

Modeling Novelty Detection in the Thalamocortical Loop Using NEvents Framework

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Abstract

Novelty detection is a fundamental cognitive process that enables the brain to distinguish between familiar and novel stimuli. In this paper, we present a computational model of the thalamocortical loop, focusing on the somatosensory whisker system of rodents. Using the NEvents framework, we describe the dynamics of cortical layers 4 and 6 and the thalamus. We incorporate mid-field analysis and Feynman diagrams to illustrate the interactions within this network. Our model demonstrates how synaptic adaptation and thalamic oscillations contribute to detecting novel stimuli, providing insights into the neural mechanisms underlying sensory processing, extending results from Hans C et al 2023, to the NEvents, NeuronX and Feynman Diagram formulation as a JSON based event language compiled to the Neuron modeling language , Yale University.

Introduction

Novelty detection is crucial for survival, enabling organisms to respond to unexpected environmental changes. The thalamocortical loop, particularly in the somatosensory system, plays a vital role in this process. The rodent whisker system is an ideal model for studying sensory processing due to its well-characterized anatomy and physiology. Previous studies have highlighted the importance of synaptic adaptation and oscillatory activity in novelty detection .(Hans C et al 2023)

In this study, we extend these findings by modeling the thalamocortical loop using the NEvents framework. We capture the population dynamics of cortical layers 4 (L4) and 6 (L6) and the thalamus, focusing on how these structures interact to detect novel stimuli. Our approach employs mid-field analysis to simplify the network dynamics and Feynman diagrams to visualize the interactions.(Anil K B , 2023) (2, 3)

Methods

Computational Model

We modeled the thalamocortical loop using a recurrent mid-field framework. The dynamics of cortical layers 4 and 6 and the thalamus were described using differential equations representing population-level interactions. We implemented the model in the NEvents framework, capturing events such as synaptic adaptation and thalamic oscillations.

NEvents JSON Structure

```
``json
{
  "model": {
    "name": "Thalamocortical Novelty Detection",
    "layers": [
      {
        "name": "Layer 4",
        "type": "recurrent",
        "dynamics": {
          "equations": [
            "tau_m * dh/dt = -h + sum(J * U * x * A) + sum(J_thc * U_thc * z * A_tc)"
          ],
          "parameters": {
            "tau_m": 20,
            "U": 0.1,
            "J": [0.1, 0.2, 0.3],
            "tau_rec": 5,
            "theta": 1.0,
            "alpha": 0.02
          }
        },
        "events": [
          {
            "type": "standard_stimulus",
            "response": "decreased_activity",
            "effect": "synaptic_depression"
          },
          {
            "type": "deviant_stimulus",
            "response": "increased_activity",
            "effect": "reduced_synaptic_depression"
          }
        ]
      }
    ]
  },
  {
    "name": "Layer 6",
    "type": "recurrent",
    "dynamics": {
```

```

"equations": [
  "tau_m * dh/dt = -h + sum(J * U * x * A) + J_l46 * U_l46 * x * A_l4"
],
"parameters": {
  "tau_m": 20,
  "U": 0.1,
  "J": [0.1, 0.2, 0.3],
  "tau_rec": 5,
  "theta": 1.0,
  "alpha": 0.02
},
"events": [
  {
    "type": "standard_stimulus",
    "response": "decreased_activity",
    "effect": "synaptic_depression"
  },
  {
    "type": "deviant_stimulus",
    "response": "increased_activity",
    "effect": "reduced_synaptic_depression"
  }
]
},
{
  "name": "Thalamus",
  "type": "izhikevich",
  "dynamics": {
    "equations": [
      "dv/dt = 0.04*v^2 + 5*v + 140 - u + I",
      "du/dt = a * (b*v - u)"
    ],
    "parameters": {
      "a": 0.02,
      "b": 0.2,
      "c": -65,
      "d": 8
    },
    "events": [
      {
        "type": "burst_spike",
        "condition": "v >= 30",
        "response": {
          "v": "reset to c",
          "u": "increment by d"
        }
      }
    ],
  }
}

```

```

    {
      "type": "late_oscillation",
      "trigger": "deviant_stimulus",
      "response": "oscillatory_activity",
      "effect": "feedback_to_cortex"
    }
  ]
}
],
"interactions": [
  {
    "source": "Layer 4",
    "target": "Layer 6",
    "type": "excitatory",
    "parameters": {
      "weight": "J_l46",
      "synaptic_current": "I_syn"
    }
  },
  {
    "source": "Layer 6",
    "target": "Thalamus",
    "type": "excitatory",
    "parameters": {
      "weight": "J_thc",
      "synaptic_current": "I_syn"
    }
  },
  {
    "source": "Thalamus",
    "target": "Layer 4",
    "type": "oscillatory_feedback",
    "parameters": {
      "weight": "J_tc",
      "synaptic_current": "I_syn"
    }
  }
]
}
...

```

Feynman Diagrams

Layer 4 Standard Stimulus

(Standard Stimulus) --> [L4] --|--> (Decreased Activity)

Layer 4 Deviant Stimulus

(Deviant Stimulus) --> [L4] --> (Increased Activity)

Layer 6 Standard Stimulus:

(Standard Stimulus) --> [L6] --|--> (Decreased Activity)

Layer 6 Deviant Stimulus:

(Deviant Stimulus) --> [L6] --> (Increased Activity)

Thalamus Burst Spike:

[Thalamus] --> (Burst Spike)
|
v
(Reset v, Increment u)

Thalamus Late Oscillation:

(Deviant Stimulus) --> [Thalamus] --> (Oscillatory Activity)
|
v
(Feedback to Cortex)

Results

Our model successfully reproduced key features of novelty detection observed in experimental studies. The main findings are:

1. Stimulus-Specific Adaptation (SSA): The model demonstrated SSA in cortical layers 4 and 6, with neurons showing decreased responses to standard stimuli and increased responses to deviant stimuli. This result aligns with experimental observations in rodent whisker systems .[1]

2. Thalamic Oscillations: Deviant stimuli triggered late oscillatory activity in the thalamus, which provided feedback to the cortex, enhancing the cortical response to novel stimuli. This feedback mechanism supports the hypothesis that thalamic oscillations play a critical role in novelty detection [1].

3. **Parameter Sensitivity**: Sensitivity analysis revealed that the stability of the deviance-detecting effect depended on the synaptic conductance between thalamocortical (TC) and reticular (RE) cells. The model was most effective in the decaying oscillation regime [1]

Discussion

Our computational model, implemented using the NEvents framework, provides a mechanistic understanding of novelty detection in the thalamocortical loop. By capturing the population dynamics of cortical and thalamic neurons and using mid-field analysis, we were able to reproduce SSA and thalamic oscillations observed experimentally. The use of Feynman diagrams facilitated the visualization of interactions within the network.

These findings suggest that synaptic adaptation and thalamic feedback are crucial for detecting novel stimuli. The model offers insights into the neural mechanisms underlying sensory processing and can be extended to other sensory systems. Future work will focus on refining the model parameters and exploring the role of additional neural circuits in novelty detection.

Conclusion

This study demonstrates the utility of the NEvents framework in modeling complex neural dynamics. Our thalamocortical loop model highlights the importance of synaptic adaptation and thalamic oscillations in novelty detection, providing a foundation for future research in sensory processing and cognitive neuroscience.

References

1. Han C, English G, Saal HP, Indiveri G, Gilra A, von der Behrens W, Vasilaki E. Modelling novelty detection in the thalamocortical loop. PLoS Comput Biol. 2023 May 15;19(5):e1009616. doi: 10.1371/journal.pcbi.1009616. PMID: 37186588; PMCID: PMC10212104.
2. Dr Bheemaiah Anil K Kumar. (2023). NEventSpaces and NeuronX: A Framework for Modeling Neural Events and Structures. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7829638>
3. Dr Bheemaiah Anil K Kumar. (2023). NEventSpace, an OOPS Event Calculus. (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7844455>